

REFLECTIONS OF LIGHTING ELEMENTS ON VISUAL PERCEPTION IN HISTORICAL STRUCTURES

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Abstract

The reflections of today's world's dizzying technical and technological developments make it feel almost every way. From communication technology to defense industry, service production to healthcare technologies, the concept of technology that is in every conceivable area makes it feel intensely in lighting systems, as predicted. By the time the fire was found, humanity sought to escape the darkness, along with the invention of fire, to provide visual comfort and convenience to individuals in the lighting field, as well as warm-up or cooking. The lighting used in the past as a key lighting element provides visual contributions to ensure a wide range of psychological and perceptual interactions today, and is particularly rich in building facades.¹ The accelerated development of lighting technology has contributed a great deal to the creation of structural fiction that is also exciting in architecture, and in particular, the lighting of historical structures gives an identity to both the structure and the area of the structure. Modern lighting technologies, on the other hand, enable the creation of authenticity in structures, while front lighting, which is unanalyzed without good analysis, can also cause considerable damage to the visual texture and historical values of structures. In this respect, it is important to select the architectural lighting criteria to be applied on the construction front.

As a result of serious developments in technology since the last century, variations in lighting concepts have also begun. The lighting is implemented in conjunction with modern lighting luminaires placed on historical sites and contributes to both urban silhouette and urban fabric. Modern lighting elements provide identity to the city, as well as the creation of a warm urban space atmosphere² The creation of attractive atmospheres also has positive results on human perception, thus opening the way for the development of such living areas in the tourism economy. With the lighting of historical sites, increasing the appeal of these structures is helping to develop social interactions and trade in these areas. In this respect, lighting designs

¹ The increasing development of lighting systems day by day allows construction of more complex and more dynamic structures in the building sector.

² Night lighting or animations on historical structures allow people to be drawn to these areas and their spaces become living with people.

should not only be satisfied with the standards in this area, but should be well analyzed in social, economic and environmental factors, particularly esthetic elements.

The lighting of structures in the status of cultural presence itself is an especially important design problem, while the historical structures of those structures symbolize the cities, they are in make lighting designs that will be implemented on these structures much more critical. The lighting architecture of historical structures, especially in cities that are in the forefront of historical identity, and in the landmark state of the city, is an increasingly common building practice in both our country and around the world. The study covers the principles of lighting designs of historical structures and reflections of the principles of practice in the individual psychology and visual perception.

Keywords: Historical structures, facade lighting, visual perception, urban icon

Introduction

From the moment humankind began to exist on earth, humankind has made many inventions to meet its individual needs. Lighting is one of the oldest inventions. This process, which began with the discovery of fire, has been able to achieve by developing with the invention of electricity to the present day. Before the discovery of fire, humanity, who tried to take advantage of the sun and the moon at night to find a place and direction, began to spend their nights more safely after the discovery of fire, and in that sense, human efficiency extended to night processes, and invention and human development began to grow exponent. In the first place, the process of lighting with the burning of resin tree leaves followed by the burning of torches created by ivy branches. This development has allowed one to take the light where it goes in mobility. The evolving and changing lighting process is: Ciro, kerosene, candles, candles, it continued with air-gas lighting and ultimately electrical lighting systems.

The concept of lighting, which is essential to life and healthy living, has demonstrated itself through the analysis of natural lighting in building architectures and has been adopted as one of the most essential elements of natural light structure architectures throughout the extended periods. The structures, illuminated by natural sun and moonlight in the first architectural shelters and directed accordingly, have been structural changes along with the invention of fire and are designed to match fire. Both lighting and cooking and the fire used as a heating tool has become the giving up of the sitting and cooking parts of the houses. In addition to the invention of electrical and electrical-dependent artificial lighting elements, architectural structures have become like today's modern structures and have evolved and today's structures at the end of the day.

With the presence of lighting elements, depending on electricity and electricity, life mobility has reached from day to night and extended human daily activity times.³ Today, nightlife shows itself in a wide range of social interactions and activities around the world. Every culture has its own needs and habits, and every culture has its own diversity of culture and life. The continued existence of life throughout the world at night has led to the need for architectural structures to join the nocturnal life. At first, lighting elements associated only with interior constructions are also included in building facades, along with today's evolving lighting technologies.

Urban images, which are key roper points, are bodily in the subjective and objective analysis of individuals. Objective analysis as subjective analysis develops perceptual, light, odor, sound, etc. it is shaped by objective factors. Light elements that enable awareness of surrounding details through sensory consequences caused by light reaching the eye create awareness for the night periods of urban life.

Well-designed urban lighting is the result of both functional and physiological requirements, while the emphasis on the material and spiritual privileges of the city and the enrichment of the city's image. The historical structures that the cities have within them, together with these lighting technologies, are attracting tourists by creating interest in publicity and influencing. The cities that interest tourists are more private in urban entrepreneurship and urban economy. Many historic urban areas today are marketed by night looks rather than daytime looks and are transformed into landmarks that are known for their nightlife thanks to the possibilities of lighting techniques. In this respect, local governments of cities with historical landmarks have a purpose for the restoration and lighting of historical structures, monuments or statues within the framework of today's urban development. Many historic cities that have become branded in this regard are subject to lighting practices in the special urban lighting expert plans, which are considered both spatial attributes and existing requirements. In the organization of main plan work for lighting, urban image, space perception, psychological approach, analytical approach, topics such as urban lighting designs, levels of illumination, night function domination, urban reading and accessibility are highlighted.

The lighting of structures on the outside face is an exceptionally large work area. The night lighting of the exterior surfaces of the structures should not be considered purely esthetic-based. Such lighting contributes to increased awareness and awareness of the city, strengthening perceptions, and the removal of psychological trauma and fears caused by night darkness, and to providing inner-city trust, peace and peace. Since historical structures, which have not been restored and have been released, can create serious security issues in the night processes, they should be restored, deployed for the purpose of their construction or for other services, and the front and recreation areas should be illuminated and made part of the cities that live at night. Individuals living in cities that can achieve these things will be healthier in the context of visual perception and psychological integrity. Because the enlightened structures will increase interest, increase interest will strengthen social integration, increase tourism interest in urban areas that can achieve social integration, and ultimately, tourism interest will bring economic

³ With electricity being included in daily life, people's activities during the day have significantly extended. This has led to the emergence of more thinking, more working, more socializing, and, in the end, a faster-growing human being.

development and prosperity. As Maslow pointed out in his theory of needs, people will move to the next level as they complete their needs. Economic prosperity will make people feel more comfortable in a psychological way, increasing interest in culture, sports and education, which will accelerate human development.

Whether open to knowledge and learning or closed, every society must live in its own dimensions and criteria, open to the future and development. This is as natural as human life from the past to the future. In this respect, the historical formations of cities should not be considered separate from culture, as societies have progressed continuously in the wave of development and change, along with their historical powers from the past. Because every city is a sign of civilization.

The main goal in lighting historic urban architectural structures is to enable night-time use of the structural whole, enrich visual conditions, contribute to the healthy progress of both pedestrian and vehicle traffic, highlight historical urban values and create esthetic cities. In this respect, it is essential to make identical lighting designs with the historical and cultural fabric of the city. The main purpose of lighting designs is to make light designs of that city, as well as visually beautifying the city.⁴ For example, the lighting of spiritual cities such as Mecca, Medina or Jerusalem, and the lighting of cities such as Paris, Las Vegas cannot be expected to be identical. On the other hand, only structural lighting does not provide the full benefits of the city, but also the light pollution, one of the most important problems of our age. Light pollution is the ability of light beams to float into the sky because the level of light required for the earth is not designed correctly.⁵ This becomes a mess in the night lighting of cities and plays a role in preventing the star and planet feast covering the city at night. Because it has genes that are inherently associated with nature by human creation, it is inevitable that it will be affected psychologically when it sees the chaos of light beams instead of the beauty in the night sky. All these things should be avoided by the structures that make up the night slushing and lighting designs that create light pollution in the surrounding lighting of the structures. Specific hierarchical regulations must be made in the number of structures in relation to the severity of the structures, especially in residential areas where multiple historical architectural structures are combined, by creating regional lighting plans specific to those areas. As the areas and structures mentioned show the city's identity, care must be taken to ensure that these places are properly recognized.

The main purpose of the facade lighting of architectural historical structures is to make such esthetics visible at night and contribute to urban esthetics for the city and its visitors. On the other hand, it will not be the right conclusion to look at the whole matter only in the context of making the structure visible. Architectural structures with historical and esthetic value must also be emphasized on the facade lighting of these structures and their characteristics of operation. If this is done, the attractiveness and appreciation of historical architectural structures will increase even further in the visual image. In addition to esthetic and qualified designs, economism is a critical issue in lighting the building facades. Especially in an age that needs to

⁴ When deciding on the lighting designs of historical structures, criteria such as which geography and culture the structure belongs to, what purpose the structure is used for, and the purpose of today's use must be kept in the foreground.

⁵ Light pollution is one of the most important problems of the modern age. Lighting in the wrong area, in the wrong direction and in the wrong amount, and even at the wrong time is one of the main causes of light pollution in cities.

be sensitive in the context of energy consumption, the selection and design of the lighting elements of structures must be conducted meticulously. It is important to note that both extreme lighting and underlighting will result in extra and unnecessary energy consumption. This should be considered in multi-dimensional terms, as this may cause negative psychological effects and perceptions as well as energy consumption.

LED lighting systems should be preferred in modern façade lighting designs. Because LED lighting systems are manufactured in smaller dimensions than traditional lamp species and can be more easily integrated with building architecture. On the other hand, while traditional lighting systems provide a static understanding of lighting, LED lighting systems can create dynamic and variable alternatives. Also, with LED systems; Lighting, wall stripping, emphasis lighting, silhouette lighting, contour lighting, passing light lighting and media facade techniques can also be created, and this increases the diversity of design in building facade visualization.

The exterior lighting of historical cultural assets requires different application techniques than other modern structures, as per their status. They are headed by a board-approved lighting design. For these kinds of structures, such as random anchoring's, assembly, drilling, etc. applications are not possible.⁶ In this respect, it is necessary to treat these lighting systems more sensitively when they are secured to the front surfaces. As well as the quality of the esthetic appearance and the ability of the structure to be perceived by the individual in terms of the life of the structure will vary depending on these criteria. The basic purpose of creating the most accurate design with minimal intervention must be obtained. The main criteria in the context of the facade lighting design of an architectural structure with historical value in general are esthetics, structural architectural integrity, visual perception and comfort creation, quality analysis of environmental factors, structural sustainability, installation,⁷ design in the energy efficiency focus, to give the structure additional dimensions, with architectural attributes and emphasis on social and historical significance, to provide a clear night environment that can positively improve structure-specific observations and experiences, it can be listed as the creation of a structure that can support security and provide comfortable navigation areas during the night process, and the construction lighting to contribute to the local economy and its icon. On the other hand, the facade lighting of historical cultural assets, the characteristics of urban residents or urban users, the function of the structure planned to be illuminated, the distribution of light levels in the region, environmental shadowing's and so on.

Vision and Detection

Approximately 1/3 of the human brain cortex and approximately 40% of the message channels function in the visual system focus. Visual sense is an active system in the detection of light or colors, as well as eye-first in the detection of three-dimensional space and distances. The eyeball

⁶ Any modifications and modifications designed on historical structures registered under the Law on Protection of historical Cultural Assets must be approved by the relevant protection board, where the historical structure is located.

⁷ The installation, also known as the art of placement, is the type of art that does not include an art object independent of the environment, apart from traditional works of art, but also uses the attributes of the structure or space created and created and created in the interior or outside space.

is supported by the oil tissue surrounding it, which is in the area called the eyeball within the eye structure. The skin layer on the outer layer of the eye provides the durability of the eyeball. This layer also can shape the eye beyond robustness. This section of the sclera layer, which is transparent in the front section, is called the cornea layer. The light entering the eye from this layer is broken by the lens in the eye, and the light that covers the inner surface of the eye is reduced to the layer of retina, and the light that falls into this area is converted into electrical current and transmitted to the visual center in the brain via the visual limit.

In general, the eye reacts to three basic unifying colors, such as red, green and blue. In this respect, the human brain perceives other colors as different combinations of these three basic colors. Color perceptions from the individual's eyes vary depending on the external environment. The same color, for example, can be detected in different shades in sunlight, different shades in moonlight. On the other hand, the quality of the vision adapts to the source of light and is perceived to be the same color seen in both the sun and the moonlight. The other essential element in the detection of colors varies depending on which lighting system the colored objects are viewed under. A painted area with any color is perceived differently next to the sun, shaded environment, artificial light or a different color. Another element that is effective in color perception is the direction of the location it is in. For example, a color designed to create a specific effect in a southern-facing place will not have the same effect in a north-facing location.

The rays from the source of the sun to the earth are made up of particles called photons, which are radiated by wave movements. These photons, which fall on any object in the area we live in, are transforming into wavelengths that reflect colors by striking the atoms of pigment molecules in the object they touch. As a result of the collision's interaction, atoms send photons outwards, and the colors generated by the photons sent are heading toward the human brain. Visual stimulation through several complex processes is staged in the brain and the visual process is completed. To summarize, the visual process is progressing in the form of light, objects, visual events and visual stimulation generated in the eyes, the physiological structure of the eye and the brain.

Lighting Systems Used in Historical Structures and Their Impact on Individual Perception

The simpler the lighting that is created to remove any space from the night darkness, the more difficult and complex processes participate in creating places that are lit so that people can enjoy it. Light sources can highlight lines within the structure. The eye, the most crucial factor in the individual's perception of information, is approximately 90% of the entire detection process. A significant part of the fatigue effects on individuals are due to eye strain during the day.

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The term "lux" (lx) is used to measure the illumination intensity. The value represents the flow of light that hits the unit area. On a sunny and light day, the intensity of the lighting is estimated at approximately 100,000 lux. In the cloudy winter days, this rate travels at three thousand lux levels. No matter how well any architecture is designed, it will not be able to capture the potential for successful design when it is not properly lit fasciately.

In the design of lighting systems, it should be aimed at ensuring visual comfort conditions first. Quality lighting equipment can be created in combination with the combination of physiological and psychological comfort and visual comfort. The physiological comfort mentioned here is provided by the quantitative dimensions of the lighting elements that can be measured, and psychological comfort is provided by the qualitative size of the lighting elements. The ability to provide individual psychological comfort will vary depending on biform,⁸ lighting, nervous systems and hormones. The detection of lighting systems by individual is initiated by moving forward in the data collection process with physical environmental impact. Environmental warnings affect the nervous system and this way the detection process is entered. Dark and light perceptions dominate this primary sense stage. After that, secondary feelings of fresh, creepy, gloomy or relaxed begin to develop, with the effect of the mental stages. The secondary feelings mentioned are different from individual to individual, as they form as reaction behaviors to physical environmental impact. The combination of both knowledge and perception is a combination of a wide range of elements. Influential factors such as cultural differences, age, gender, education, experience, play an active role in the diversity of choice of lighting systems. This election also activates individual hormonal systems. Both hormones and interactions in the nervous system are perceived in the focus of the environment, structure or location; light, dark, dim, gloomy, tractor, serene, etc. the adjectives are defined in the brain.

It is essential to know the importance of both psychological and physiological interactions in building lighting and to reflect them on relevant designs. When designing the lighting system for any structure, it is necessary to analyze the cultural, historical and architectural characteristics of the region where it was originally located in the urban area. The analysis should cover a wide range of functional and architectural features of the structure, from production techniques. The intended lighting system must adapt to both the architectural character and the use of the structure.

In the creation of a qualified lighting project, the facility of positive perception, particularly eye health, is of immense importance. Because it is a fact that lighting systems affect both the biological structure of the individual and its bio-rightism. Depending on the level and severity of the luminance found in the environment, some hormones in the body are known to have increased or decreased. In northern Scandinavian countries, where daylight hours are short, this problem occurs with the beginning of autumn and winter seasons and is defined as SAD

Developed by Wilhelm Fliess in the 19th century, the concept of Bioritm reveals that different processes in individuals' lives can be estimated in line with simple mathematical calculations.

Syndrome (Seasonal Affective Disorder). Individuals who are exposed to such problems can be treated using artificial light sources whose spectral layout is equivalent to daylight.

The effects of lighting effects on individuals are not just seasonal focused. The environments in which individuals are present can also create this interaction. Based on photometric changes in the environment conditions found, both the hormone and the nervous system interact and cause changes in signals reaching the brain. This also creates changes in the activity level and muscle mobility of the individual. Having researched the issue, Bommel stated that the insulin levels and heart rates in individuals' blood have changed depending on the light level. On the other hand, the change in working conditions and times also influences the individual's biorhythms. The effect presents problems such as sleep disorder, fatigue, memory loss or reduction, stomach and digestive disorders, distraction and inability to adapt. Braniard and Glickman's research revealed that individuals who have frequent changes in working hours experience more intense heart disorders and psychological problems, depending on the deformity in bio-rhythm balances. It has also been observed that, because of research, the cortisone epidemics in individuals in places where there is no front opening are significantly reduced, that the individual experiences mental discomfort and consequently has decreased motivation and efficiency. As a result, there are adverse effects on the individual's immune system and drops in body resistance. The ashes and Wetterberg conducted experimental research on the issue and obtained results in the correct proportion of this situation in two groups of experiments with psychological treatment in two unusual places with and without facade clearance. According to this, the subjects who were treated in a place without a front opening were unable to predict the time they were in the environment. In addition, the hallucinations of these subjects have increased twice as much as the subjects found in the areas of the facade. The design of lighting systems directly affects the individual. In this respect, the qualitative determination of lighting systems is important, such as lighting intensity, direction of light, ghosting effects, light distribution on the surface or atmosphere, level of benefit from lighting, inability to prevent glare, light color and reflection.

To properly and quality design and implement lighting systems, these areas should be directly targeted and avoid eye-catching directives in lighting areas and surfaces. Because for the eye that understands something clearly at last source, this creates a disturbing and exhausting feeling. For these surfaces, it is essential to create dominant directional light areas and to ensure alignment of the surface gradient in the lighting of recessed facades. On the other hand, the level of light on the surface that is intended to be highlighted in the front lighting should be greater than the environmental illumination ratio. Because on surfaces that do not have light sources in their own body, the contours of the surface in question coincide with the reflection factor of the surface and the level of light on that surface. In this respect, the dark surface needs to be more illuminated at certain proportions so that they appear at the same level of light on the two surfaces mentioned in a structure with dark and light surfaces. The proper radiated lighting design, which would mean nothing to the lighting of the exterior surfaces of the

structure, should be avoided, by analyzing the surface of the structure, to highlight the tagines in this area and to highlight the architectural expression, to create effective lighting levels.

The concept of light that allows the appearance of objects in our world and the color on those objects to be distinguished is a design awareness that is used extensively in the field of architecture. Light is a quality that creates space and building surfaces in structures, as well as a key role in contributing to the esthetic integrity of structures. And in the urban whole and atmosphere, it's obvious that structures equipped with lighting systems create different perceptions on people in the context of day and night images. In emphasizing the night view of any architectural structure, esthetic values such as color, material choices, front contrasts, are reflected in the technological advances in lighting systems. In today's world, building lighting designs have become more of a symbol of prestige and success than a need.

With the implementation of technologies in lighting systems, many artifacts that make up the artificial environment have begun to gain new identities. In this context, the desired effect to be created with light and color components can be visually presented on the structural surfaces. It is possible that the same structure can be detected in diverse ways as the variation of lighting in variable color. In this respect, different dimensions can be added based on visual detection on the building surfaces, along with different shades of light.

With the development of lighting technology, it is possible to create flexible designs for lighting architectural structures. Modern lighting systems, such as LED technology and fiber optic technology, can be combined with lighting designs on the building facades in a way that radiates both the point and the building surface. On the other hand, with lighting systems integrated with computer technology, variable light levels or color and dynamic variable light images on the building surfaces have become applicable. Examples of computer-aided lighting systems can be shown by tapping on the building facades. This makes it possible to apply unlimited effects and animation.

Image 1. Night view of Rion-Antirion Bridge with LED Lighting System (Trikoupis, Greece)

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Source: <https://www.roadtraffic-technology.com/projects/rion-antirion/>

The lighting systems are mainly collected under three headings as conventional, architectural and dynamic lighting. Conventional lighting has high power and wide-angle light distribution projectors for the facility of homogeneous diffusion lighting on the construction facades. To ensure the desired light distribution on the construction facades in conventional lighting, the lighting luminaires are secured to the ground by moving them away from the structure at certain proportions. With this system, the architectural features of the structure are intended to appear as light appears on a day. However, conventional lighting requires a distance enough to accommodate the construction and lighting systems and is intended to avoid people passing through this range. Because for individuals who pass through the range between the light and the structure reflected at a distance to the structure, this area will have a disturbing effect. Such lighting is considered suitable for historic forts, historic periods or towers and high-build buildings, which are not used overnight and are wanted to contribute to the night silhouette of the remote city.⁹ It should not be considered because of the psychological discomfort of the confined space and the low-rise structures.

Image 2. Royal Stockholm Palace exterior conventional lighting (Stockholm Palace, Sweden)

Source: http://www.tunliweb.no/SM/alb_stockholm.htmentry&id=524&lang=09_

⁹ Conventional lighting is created by a dense and powerful light source projecting from a distance to the structure to the construction front. This is not a preferred type of lighting for structures where interior is actively used at night. We are looking at historic forts, walls or monuments that are less or less open to the front as a suitable application for lighting monuments.

The other lighting systems are architectural lighting. These types of lighting, which can be applied in different techniques, such as wall stripping, accent, silhouette and passing contours, are hidden lighting luminaires placed on the facades to highlight architectural details on the building facades. Unlike conventional lighting, the main purpose of architectural lighting is to provide different and selective views to the fabric facades. Mini projectors with high light efficiency are preferred, especially when lighting architectural details. On the other hand, it is not far from the structure, such as conventional lighting, but rather, it is integrated into the structure, so it should be treated with much more precision, especially in assemblies to the facades of historical structures.

Image 3. Palais Palace of Justice exterior architectural lighting (Palais de Justice, Lyon)

Source: <https://www.lightzoomlumiere.fr/realisation/palais-de-justice-de-lyon-lumiere-et-temporalite/>

The lighting system, known as the wall stripping technique, is the most used technique for architectural front lighting. In conventional lighting technique, the light source is reflected from a certain distance to the structure, reducing shadow lengths on the surface of the structure, while the light reaches the surface at a very bent angle due to light sources positioned too close to the face surface of the wall stripping technique. Thanks to this technique, the light grazes the surface, allowing the three-dimensional texture of the surface materials to be noticeably clear. Along with wall stripping technique, the three-dimensional properties of facade materials are evident by the light stripping the tissue.

Historical structures, construction techniques and building materials have generally rough textural facades. While the rough surface mentioned during the day can be detected a little bit, the facades of historical structures that have been lit by the method of stripping walls at night appear in much more prominent ways. This makes historical structures more interesting, richer

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and more esthetic by individuals, and plays an active role in the perception of individuals creating direction or point of rotation.

Another common lighting in historical structures is emphasis lighting technique. In this technique, areas with special accents, such as sections or elements, special surfaces of structures, artistic shapes, engravings, are endowed to points and more objects or limited areas. The forces of light sources are proportional to this relative, as the targeted and focused surface or objects are smaller.

The emphasis lighting technique often uses the contrast of light color. This means that the part of the structure that is intended to be highlighted can be terminated higher than the structure itself, or it can be illuminated in assorted colors or tones than the lighting used in the entire structure. For example, the domes, columns, or minaret sections of historic mosques can be illuminated in an assorted color or light tone than the whole structure.

Another preferred lighting in historical structures is the silhouette lighting technique. This lighting style is used to illuminate the background of the surface without being illuminated. This leaves facade surfaces in the dark and provides a foreground silhouette that is the main object. In the silhouette lighting technique, illumination of the back of the main object is another practice technique. However, it is difficult to apply this technique in every architecture. Sufficient space is needed to ensure that the lighting devices with wide opening and angles are not within the individual's visual area to successfully apply the technique. Otherwise, it would be inevitable that a wide range of negative psychological effects will occur depending on the glare of individuals who see this area.

Selecting historical structures with a large column/column structure in a successful silhouette lighting will result in more accurate and successful results. This lighting technique is recommended to apply and support different lighting techniques in other parts of the structure. In this way, some of the structure's area will be illuminated, while other parts will be easier to perceive as silhouettes.

Another lighting technique that can be applied in historical structures is the passing light. This technical structure is like the silhouette lighting technique. Rather than the exterior of the structure, the indentation areas one step below the facade, or the lighting of the interior of the structure directly constitutes the basic characteristics of this technique. The specific indents, window or door displays of the structure can be lit according to this technique.

Another facade lighting technique, which is suitable for historical structures, is the contour lighting application. This technique is intended to highlight the outline of the structure through light lines. The main purpose in this lighting technique, which has point or linear properties and surrounds the outline in line with architectural properties, is to uncover the basic geometric lines of the structure rather than the visible structure.

Another type of lighting is known as dynamic lighting. There are more professional options such as lighting, image reflections, which are decorated with this type of moving and quite assorted color options. Dynamic lighting is often used, especially in applications projected on the performance fabric facades. One of the most successful dynamic lights in our country is the dynamic lighting applied to the Galata tower in Istanbul Taksim. Also St. John is a good example of such practices on the front of the cathedral.

Dynamic lighting offers a more limited time-based service than conventional and architectural lighting. These kinds of lighting are mainly celebrations, festivals, concerts, cinemas, it is applied on special days, such as theater, and often on historical structures. Since permanent dynamic displays lose interest after a while, they create a perceptual repetitive and aging feeling in individuals and are therefore a temporary use of facade lighting.

Image 4. Dynamic lighting used on the front of the Istanbul Youth Festival (2018) and Galata Tower (Taksim/İstanbul, Türkiye)

Source: <https://www.trthaber.com/haber/kultur-sanat/galata-kulesinde-video-mappingle-gorsel-solen-362586.html>

With dynamic lighting systems integrating with the historical structures, the building facades are transformed into entertainment, information, training, communication tools. This system is designed and mounted on the construction surface as well as on the contour lighting technique system.

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Structural lighting should be considered as an esthetic, as well as in the context of environmental impact. Because such practices can create beautiful feelings and environments in individual and environmental focus, as well as several negative influences. In this respect, the comprehensive approach of the matter is crucial to the creation of sensitivity to the environment and human health. For example, building front lighting can be disturbing and even deadly for several plants and animals. As a result of research, the light emitted from the systems used in the front lighting has been observed that many creatures, such as bats, frogs, lizards and birds, have created distortions in the rhythms of natural life and reproduction called "the clock that sirens".¹⁰ The facade lighting systems, which can have adverse effects on active living things at night, can have a negative effect on the feeding environment of night-hunting animals. On the other hand, these systems can create a time shift in the creatures that begin their activities with sunrise. In addition to animals, it is possible to see negative effects on plants and trees that provide movement and nutrients with sunlight. It is also possible that all animals can experience disruptions in the food chains with insects that are moving away from the environment by intense light or are concentrating on the environment. Slovenia was the first country to express and legalize the light sensitivity of animals on the continent and the world. In Slovenia, one of the most popular countries in astronomy, important lighting sanctions have been implemented to ensure birds do not fail to leave their migration routes. Birds find their route at night by looking at the stars, so when they cross the city, the light in the cities is pollutant, so they are disoriented and moving in different directions. The number of birds that change their course and cannot go where they need to go after this change is about twenty million a year, with the magic of light beams that spread from light pollution to the sky. In this respect, it is especially important not to use lighting systems in all cities, especially those that exceed the horizon and cause this insurance.

Image 5. The quality of the sky being seen when electricity is active and inactive

Source: <http://www.darksky.org/light-pollution/>

¹⁰ The Sirkadian clock is defined as the whole of psychological and biochemical behavior that plants and animals demonstrate within 24 hours of time.

Another important aspect of the lighting of historical structures and monuments within the city is that individuals living in the city and using the structure environment feel safer and more comfortable during the night period. It is a fact known that there is lighter in the urban environment or around the structure, which reduces crime rates in this region or increases security impact, but not scientific studies, but that light-up environments in many areas have a deterrent effect on people who are malicious. However, the quality of the light is more important than the quantity of light. For example, the presence of building front lighting or light systems used in environmental regulations that are located there or positioned to disturb individuals passing by could lead to security vulnerability. With the light from sources of light to their eyes dazzled, those whose vision quality is reduced will be vulnerable to the dangers that can suddenly come from their surroundings. On the other hand, this can also create risks that can cause trip, fall, injury, injury or even death, as this may influence poor visibility.

The "light pollution", known as the dark sky effect, is occurring due to light beams reflected through structures that are not well lit or flowing out of light sources that are not properly angled. Every city, badly designed for lighting, faces this pollution. The lack of sky beauty when looking at night sky also contributes negatively to the urban skyline. In this respect, the structures or space observatory houses of space observers are always positioned where the city lights cannot reach or affect them. In addition to visual and psychological effects, poorly designed sources of lighting also return as wasted energy and greenhouse gas emissions.

In addition to the lighting types mentioned above, the lighting systems that are specialized in themselves are also heavily used. It will be possible to split the lighting in the form of steady and moving lights. The main theme of this study will be given in the form of defining fixed and moving lights mentioned, as historical structures have perceptual effects created by front lighting and lighting elements. Fixed lighting consists of high-directional lighting, downwards lighting and washer lighting called wash light. Fixed lighting is created in accordance with various application guidelines, semi-recessed, surface-to-surface, apiary, or suspension. Downwards lighting is used to illuminate horizontal surfaces. On the other hand, it is possible to reposition the light source to illuminate the lateral vertical surfaces. Upward lighting is a source of light directed toward the ceiling from vertical surfaces and areas close to the ground. The floor lamp and wall form this category. One of the fixed lighting elements is the washer lights. These types of lighting are used for jobs that require proper lighting in large areas. The most important thing that it separates from other types of fixed lighting is that it does not cause hyperbolic beams on the surfaces. The moving lights are made up of spot lighting systems used in the desired positions. Spot systems are highly effective in lighting both horizontal surfaces and level surfaces as they can be moved at wide angles on the rail.

Considerations to be Considered in The Lighting of Historical Structures in Order to Create Positive Psychological Effects on The Individual

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Historical structures are the memory and symbols of cities. Every city, which is culturally oriented today, is committed to highlighting its historical structures with both social and economic goals. From this point of view, the night lighting of historical structures that make up the most important texture of the urban skyline is of immense importance. On the other hand, the lighting design should be conducted by competent people and academic minds. In this respect, it is often not necessary to illuminate all layers of any historical structure, as it may cause negative effects. In this context, the distance, perspectives or structure-oriented positions of individuals living or living in the city are of great importance in design processes.

As mentioned above, it will provide a more qualified study to keep architectural elements, such as structures, objects, columns, and so on, rather than lighting the entire structure. In this system, the repetitive or non-repetitive motifs, rendering, or emphasizing special applications of the historical structure make it easier for individuals to be perceptive and enhance their appreciation.

The use of cross, upward or background lighting in lighting designs is a common principle of historical structures. However, the upward lighting has light pollution and both the city lighting quality, and the quality of night life are reduced. This requires more rigorous designs in upper-directional lighting. Large-diameter luminaires, both mounted on the surface of the structure and positioned near the structure, can create image pollution in the daytime. In this respect, it is essential that these luminaires are camouflaged very well at the design size. On the other hand, it is especially important to create designs, considering both the installation and maintenance phases of luminaires, so that qualified applications can be performed. Because these luminaires are clearly located in open spaces, the rain, snow, hail, storm, solar rays, damage caused by reptile animals that can fly or climb the structure must not be ignored. Failure and replacement of a luminaire located in difficult areas as location and access may not be possible at any time but may result in significant accidents during the change. The effects on visual perception will also be adversely improved, as long-term unchanged luminaires will cause poor appearance of historical structures in front tissues. The lighting to increase the appeal of the structure and therefore the city will have an opposite effect, reducing the interest and positive perception of the structure and the city. No individual will want to look at the disturbing image created by a constantly blinking luminaire because it is deteriorated and avoid being around the structure in question.

Another important aspect of lighting historic structures is the state of light sources from neighboring settlements around the historical structure or from the near-environmental environment of the historical structure. In this respect, this should not be passed out before lighting design, the historical structure should not be dealt with individually, and the design of lighting should be planned along with its nearby surroundings. On the other hand, if the historical structure is not built-in proximity, the implementation of the lighting intensity on any historical structure in the city will also lead to a false design result. This should be considered in the interest of both visual quality and economic use of energy consumption.

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Another thing to note about the front lighting of historical structures is how clean the facade sizes and building surfaces of the relevant structures are. On the other hand, the projecting properties of materials used on historical building surfaces also play a significant role in the selection of lighting type and intensity. In addition, if historical structures are higher-ply or geographically higher than their surrounding structures, it is a good approach to keeping the levels of front lighting at lower levels than planned.

In addition to human perceptions in lighting, animal reactions need to be professionally researched. This will result in a more environmentally sustainable design. The natural life of the region should also be taken into consideration in lighting designs, especially animals that have nested in the environment, hunt at night, or are highly light-sensitive.

Light source selections also play a key role in the creation of successful designs in the lighting of historical structures. Light efficiency is defined by the ratio of the light axle against the power consumed. This rate is known as lumen/watt. In this context, a lighting system with a good lumen/watt ratio will create both less energy consumption and provide the planned level of light with less energy consumption. The other important thing about this planning is the efficiency of the lighting luminaire, which is connected to the light source. This efficiency is expressed in the form of "light Output Ratio/LOR". The overall efficiency in the system will vary in relation to this ratio. On the other hand, in light source preferences, the color temperature of that source, the kelvin value, and color feedback called color rendering index/CRI should be considered. The use of light sources with high CRI values is essential for quality display of the surface colors of historical structures and the creation of accurate perceptions in individuals. On the other hand, the effects of color temperatures on historical building materials should also be considered in the planning process.

Environmental impacts can have a negative impact on the lighting of historical structures, which can cause the structure to be perceived as being worse than it is. To eliminate this immortality, the dominance of the multi-dimensional design thinking is crucial. Even the color and intensity of environmental lighting should be included in design processes. In fact, if necessary, alterations in the direction of environmental lighting, violence or color of environmental lighting should be requested by collaborating with local governments. If this is not possible, the tones should be preferred to highlight so that the structure can be separated from other color lighting. In addition, the green structure evaluation criteria for determining the lighting levels should be taken into consideration. These criteria define the light intensity listed from LZ0 to LZ4. LZ0 Lighting of buildings or areas without environmental lighting, lighting LZ1 parks or rural areas, lighting LZ2 residential or residential lighting, lighting LZ3 commercial, industrial or high-density residential areas, LZ4 lighting main urban centers or recreational centers. The LZ1 dark, LZ2 low, LZ3 medium, LZ4 high light zones are represented here. For qualified lighting designs to be realized at these scales, it is necessary to determine which monuments or structures are within the zone range. On the other hand, the coefficients of reflecting the light that the building surfaces of historical structures have played a key role in the accurate detection

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of these structures. In addition, activity concentrations around the structure are among the key drivers in the design of lighting systems. Another crucial point in the design phase is to provide the visual hierarchy between architectural elements of historical structures and parts of the structure other than those elements. To create this effect, architectural elements on the historical structure need to be illuminated at higher levels of light. On the other hand, the light or dark effects created on the structure are all shaped around the perception element. Accordingly, lighting in an area where low levels of light exist and lighting designs in an area with elevated levels of lighting will produce different results.

Another important aspect of historical structures of front lighting is the design of these lighting systems in combination with control systems. Lighting systems with a control system will automatically switch on, saving energy and automatically detecting day and night changes. This topic should be discussed with precision, as it will have significant consequences on perception and human psychology. In manual systems, it is almost impossible to activate the front lighting systems daily at the exact time. Temporal deviations and setback will always occur in human-hand controls, causing time deviations in the time perceptions of individuals living or living around the structure for an extended period. On the other hand, it is also possible to adjust the lighting intensity in a seasonal focus or focused on the circulation intensity around the structure, along with automated systems. This enables sensors integrated into the structure to be activated and converted into an organic structure that lives with the surrounding historical structures during less concentrated time zones or periods.

Another important aspect of the installation of qualified lighting systems is to ensure that designs are conducted in a virtual environment prior to implementation with 3D modeling tools. With this approach, mistakes that may arise during or after the application and cannot be foreseen can be avoided and additional time and money consumption can be avoided. In addition, the cost of making 3D models is much lower than the cost of implementing them, so the design process is designed with 3D variations of desired variability, making it possible to implement the design that produces the most successful and positive results on perception.

Results and Recommendations

The characteristics of the historical monuments found in the cities must be analyzed correctly. It is important to determine the work or structures that are expected to be prioritized, especially in areas where historical structures or groups of artifacts are together, because it is not possible to brighten up at the same rate, and the perceptual emphasis effects on structures may be lost even if they can be illuminated. When deciding which works or structures to illuminate, many criteria should be considered, such as environmental conditions, user activities, region requirements and general region characteristics.

Structural integrity will be achieved when the design of locations includes dimensional requirements, as well as the mental and psychological requirements of users. In this context,

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physical and psychological requirements are not only the subject of the interior of the structure, but also the exterior structure and lighting.

It plays a key role in the exterior lighting, as well as the architectural and visual elements of the structure, as well as what it was designed for and built for. Hospital, caravan, medrese, sanctuary, library, building light designs in each of the historic buildings designed for many purposes, such as the hammam, the government building, will make it easy to detect the building correctly.

It is known that the color images provided by lighting and lighting affect individuals both psychologically and physiologically. In this respect, it is essential that the positive side of these elements be made available to users by using them through qualified designs. Ergonomics, structure biology, chemistry, structure physics, medicine, especially lighting element architecture, it is a whole that influences many sciences, such as anatomy and biomaterials.¹¹ From the data obtained as a result of the scientific research in this respect, it should be considered how the types of lighting affect the health of individuals, and the design of human and vibrant lighting should be prioritized.

The lighting of structures with historical and cultural backgrounds of cities and actively inclusion in urban life makes that city more qualified. The cities are important roper points, monuments, historic places and living and breathing organisms with historical structures. The active role of these organisms in nightlife will contribute positively to the psychological structures of both urban residents and visitors to the city. People feel safer and happier in areas where they live with themselves and have structures that reflect their own identity. Social and economic revival and development cannot be expected in the vicinity of historical structures that transition from night to day to negative. To do this, historical structures should be considered and developed at every moment of the day, with the people they host in and around them.

This study covers the perceptual effects of lighting designs in historical structures, both to building architectures and users using the structure. It has been noted that why historical structures should be considered multidimensional in lighting designs, and the visual effects of building architecture and the perceptual and psychological changes that they can create in individuals around the structure, living and using the structure, are noted. Architecture is a very wide-ranging science that requires design to be created, from city planners to civil engineering, mechanical engineering, sociology, electrical engineering, psychology, geography to climate science, literature to visual arts. The main element of this integrity is, of course, the comfort and comfort of the human being. Because every architectural structure is designed and built for human beings. The structures affect people as well as their interior and their exterior facades. The part that interacts with the individual as soon as it is out of any structure is the outer shell

¹¹ Bioharmology is defined as a branch of science that explores the harmonization between any natural or artificial physical and environmental formations that occur in the living processes of living things and develops rational solution recommendations on the subject.

structure of the structure and its immediate environment. Since the intensity of the impact on man has become even more apparent in nightlife, it is essential that structures, especially in modern life today, participate in this flow and live with the city. The needs of modern life require that historical structures be equipped with modern lighting systems, and those structures evolve in a direction that aims to enable people to participate in their life activities and provide positive visual perceptions.

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